

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

ECOLOGICAL CONSEQUENCES OF CHEMICAL POLLUTION OF ECOSYSTEMS OF UKRAINE

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ABSTRACT

Any armed conflict always causes an ecological disaster, due to large emissions of chemical substances. Russian forces are attacking port infrastructure along the Black and Azov Sea coasts and ships at anchor, causing water pollution and the spread of toxic substances into the sea. Petroleum products have a negative effect on marine biocenoses, forming films on the surface of the water, which disrupts the exchange of energy, heat, moisture and gases between the sea and the atmosphere. In addition, they directly affect physico-chemical and hydrological conditions, cause the death of fish, seabirds and microorganisms. All oil components are toxic to marine organisms. Oil has another side property. Its hydrocarbons are able to dissolve a number of other pollutants, such as pesticides, heavy metals, which, together with oil, concentrate in the near-surface layer and poison it even more.

Soil contamination with fuel and lubricants and other petroleum products occurs as a result of the movement and damage of ground military equipment. In soils impregnated with fuel and lubricants, water permeability decreases, oxygen is displaced, and biochemical and microbiological processes are disrupted. As a result, the water and air regimes and the circulation of nutrients deteriorate, the root nutrition of plants is disturbed, their growth and development are inhibited, which causes death.

Keywords: chemical pollution, ecological damage, ecosystems.

Formulation of the problem. During explosions of military shells, a huge amount of dangerous substances are released into the environment - both for humans and for other living organisms nearby. Specialists of the non-governmental organization "Ekodia" explain that some munitions may use very toxic chemical compounds, such as white phosphorus, which emits poisonous gas and causes burns when burned, and poisons soil and water if it gets into the environment. Phosphorus is practically insoluble and can be stored for decades in salty seawater under conditions of oxygen deficiency. Many compounds developed as chemical warfare agents that are highly toxic to humans are also toxic to other vertebrates at high concentrations. They can affect some aquatic organisms, as well as accumulate and persist for years in the natural environment. The danger is not only explosions, but also ships that remain permanently at sea.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Both the Black Sea and the Sea of Azov have suffered from environmental degradation for decades, which was complicated by their geographical location. The Black Sea receives the waters of three of Europe's largest rivers, and its catchment area is about five times its surface area [1]. Due to the location of large industrial

and agricultural regions in the Black Sea basin, pollution problems were widespread. The great depth of the Black Sea and its shallow periphery lead to the fact that the water does not mix well, and below 100-150 m it is almost devoid of oxygen. The Sea of Azov, on the other hand, is extremely shallow, and it is dominated by the inflow of the Don and Kuban rivers. The nutrients they brought to the shallows once supported high fish stocks, but eutrophication, pollution and overfishing have led to the degradation of the sea's ecosystem [2-4].

The main effects of war on coastal and marine ecosystems include chemical and acoustic pollution, physical damage to natural habitats, and the decline of conservation activities. Military action also hinders environmental monitoring and management of the Black and Azov Seas. Damaged industrial facilities and settlements can be important sources of chemical pollution of the coastal and marine environment [5].

The factors of mortality of marine biota also include pathogens that can get into the sea as a bacteriological weapon, or accidentally due to damage to urban sewage or an agricultural complex. Scientists discovered this pollution mechanism even before the start of a full-scale war - the Russians deliberately, in a barbaric

way, polluted their own water areas and international waters, dumping sewage from agricultural farms in the Krasnodar Territory into the sea, which caused dolphins to get toxoplasmosis [6].

Spills from ships put protected wetlands at risk, and the widespread use of sea mines increases the risk to ships and the subsequent risks of releases to the environment if they collide with mines.

In 2017, American scientists from the Argonne laboratory invented the Oleo Sponge technology. Outwardly, the invention resembles ordinary sponges for washing dishes, but the human eye cannot see the most important thing: this technology works at the nano-level. Oxidized metal atoms with complex nanostructures penetrate the fibers of the sponge, giving it the ability to effectively combine with oil in water, separating these liquids. Sponges not only clean water from oil, they store raw materials. Collected oil can be used again in production after "squeezing" the sponge. And the sponge itself can be reused. Collected oil can be used again in production after "squeezing" the sponge. And the sponge itself can be reused. This technology, according to scientists, is safe for the environment unlike other methods: modern sorbent technologies absorb oil for a single use, and then the oil-saturated materials must be disposed of. But the Oleo Sponge method is environmentally friendly—it doesn't harm marine life, animals, or the environment in general—a key advantage over chemical dispersants or incineration methods used today [7-10].

In addition to water resources, soils are also polluted. The destruction of the upper fertile layer of the soil, which was formed over centuries, occurs as a result of explosions of rockets, artillery shells of various types, high-explosive aerial bombs, drones, shells of various types of MLRS, "vacuum" bombs, etc. This is despite the fact that over the past 100 years, domestic soils have lost about 30% of humus. War accelerates this process. Soils lose their fertility due to changes in their physical, chemical, and physicochemical properties. The explosion of a projectile of any type is the entry of a number of toxic compounds into the soil. According to the specialists of the NGO "Ekodiya", during the detonation of rockets and artillery shells, carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, water vapor, nitrous oxide, nitrogen dioxide, formaldehyde, cyanic acid vapors, nitrogen, as well as a large amount of toxic organics are

formed. Soil scientists note a systematic 6-8 times excess of mercury, zinc and cadmium indicators [11-15].

The purpose of the work. The purpose of the work is a detailed coverage of the problems of chemical pollution of Ukrainian ecosystems as a result of the war.

Results. The explosions pose a serious threat to marine mammals, which are listed in the Red Book of Ukraine and protected by many international conventions. For example, all three species of dolphins that live in the Black Sea are listed in the Red Book, but dead individuals are increasingly found on the coast. Recently, inspectors of the National Park "Tuzlov Estuaries" found a dead dolphin with burnt skin - this happened due to the explosion of an underwater bomb. At the same time, dead dolphins are found not only on the Ukrainian coast. A particularly large number of dead and disoriented dolphins washed ashore was also recorded by scientists in Turkey and Bulgaria this year. Isolated cases were recorded in the northwestern part of the Black Sea, that is, in the Romanian and Ukrainian sectors of this part.

Reuters called the impact of a missile on the Moldovan-flagged tanker *Millennial Spirit*, which had been drifting in the Black Sea for more than four months, an "ecological disaster". The ship was transporting diesel fuel.

The damage from diesel fuel entering water is no less than from crude oil spills, although the consequences of both products are similar. The damage from an oil spill is very dangerous, because the oil covers the water layer with a thin film that blocks the access of oxygen to the water. As a result, algae do not receive enough light to produce oxygen, fish and fry die, which live and feed almost on the surface of the sea. Even a minimal oil spill has negative consequences for the environment. First of all, it is harmful to small organisms and plankton that float in the water column. It can also lead to the death of fish, harm oil spills and birds, which suffer by falling into "oil slicks". Oil tends to sink below the water level and form "clouds" of droplets below the surface. It is extremely difficult to collect such oil, and for its disposal sometimes environmentally dangerous methods are used, such as, for example, burning. However, in the conditions of the war, it is now impossible to do even this.

Fig.1. Oil spill in the Black Sea [16]

Fires on the coast

Another problem is that coastal ecosystems are being destroyed by fires that cannot be extinguished due to possible shelling - according to preliminary data, the fire has covered 130 hectares on the Kinburn Spit alone. Areas of forest ecosystems have been lost, rare species of animals and unique sand flora have been destroyed and damaged; birds listed in the Red Book have lost places suitable for nesting (Fig 2.).

The natural heritage of Ukrainians — national parks and natural biosphere reserves — also suffers

from the war. Currently, there is only one national natural park on the Black Sea and Azov coasts that is not occupied by the Russians - it is "Tuzlovsky lymani", the others - "Azov-Syvaskyi" park, "Dzharylgatskyi" and "Meotida" - are under occupation. These territories must be protected by the state - inspectors, park employees must go around the parks to record changes in the environment, fight poachers, etc., but due to the war, proper protection is impossible in the occupied territories, and in the non-occupied ones - it is weakened, because there is not enough staff

Fig.2. Centers of fires on the territory of Ukraine. (Source: SaveEcoBot fire map)

With the onset of spring, the fire-risk period begins and the risk of fires in ecosystems due to shelling increases. After the snow melts, last year's grass dries up, as a result of which it can quickly catch fire. In dry conditions, fires spread instantly and over large areas. In the territories occupied by Russian troops, the emergency services will not be able to work and eliminate fires. There are also favorable conditions for the spread of fires in monoculture pine plantations in the north and east of Ukraine.

In addition to forests, swamp ecosystems and peatlands are common in the north of the country, where active hostilities are taking place. Most of the peatlands of Ukraine are drained, and therefore there are favorable conditions for the occurrence of peat fires. Such fires are difficult to extinguish and, in normal times, therefore, the continuation of hostilities in the territory of the northern regions will have serious consequences for both the environment and people's health. During the burning of peatlands, such toxic substances as oxide and carbon dioxide, fine dust with a particle diameter of 2.5 microns (typical for burning), volatile organic compounds, which include acrolein and formaldehyde, are released into the air.

Consequences of fires at industrial facilities

Shelling of industrial facilities and infrastructure leads to fires, which cause additional pollution of air, soil and water. Combustion products that enter the air consist of toxic gases and solid particles. There will also be significant soil and water contamination at these sites. Where fire-fighting measures have been carried out, contamination may include residual fire-fighting foam.

Risks associated with damage to communications, enterprises, and other objects that pose an increased environmental hazard are of particular importance, because in the absence of control and opportunities to eliminate negative consequences, these phenomena potentially increase the scale of negative impact.

On February 27, 2022, the Russian military hit an oil depot in the Vasylykiv district of the Kyiv region with a ballistic missile. A fire broke out as a result of the missile strike. On the territory of the oil depot near the village of Kryachki, 10 tanks of 2000 m³ of gasoline and diesel fuel caught fire. Similar cases occurred in Okhtyrka, Luhansk, Chernihiv, Zhytomyr, Chernyakhiv. March 2022, in the village of Chayki near Kyiv, a projectile hit a warehouse with polyurethane foam, which caused a fire in the warehouse and in an office building adjacent to it. The combustion products of polyurethane foam cause poisoning of animals and people, and contribute to the appearance of acid rain. The danger of acid rain is that it causes burns to plants. This leads to a decrease in the biomass of agricultural crops, as well as to the weakening of wild plants and forest crops. Weakened forests can be quickly attacked by pests, which in turn contributes to the increase in the amount of dead wood in the forest and the spread of fires in ecosystems.

The vast majority of enemy shelling falls on peaceful territories, fields, settlements and industrial facilities. During the detonation of rockets and artillery

shells, surrounding soils, wood, turf are oxidized, and a number of chemical compounds are also formed:

- carbon monoxide
- brown gas
- nitrous oxide
- nitrogen dioxin
- formaldehyde
- a large amount of toxic organic matter.

During the explosion, all substances are completely oxidized, and the products of the chemical reaction are released into the atmosphere.

Every shelling, every explosion - the soil, water bodies, and air are contaminated with the remains of the combustion of fuel materials. These are not just explosives, but also fuel, detonators, so there is contamination with chemical compounds. First of all, heavy metals, lead. Lead compounds accumulate in the soil, in plants, and also in the human body and negatively affect mental development, the state of the bone system, and attention. Unfortunately, the lead compounds will continue to remain in the body, so we will have food contamination if we continue to try to grow in the fields where military action is taking place.

Chemical substances used in ammunition and explosives represent a long list of organic and inorganic substances, which can be divided into: potentially toxic elements (PTE), energetic compounds (EC) and chemical warfare agents (CWA). PTEs from war-affected areas are mainly Pb and its associated contaminants, including antimony, chromium, arsenic, mercury, nickel, zinc, and cadmium. Explosives contain a huge amount of Pb and Hg, in particular mercury (II) fulminate. Zn, Cu, Ni, Pb and Cr are used to coat bullets, missiles, gun barrels and military vehicles. Ba, Sb, and B are weapons charge compounds, and W is a kinetic bomb because of its high density (19.3 g/cm³).

The Dnipro River is also polluted, in particular because water supply and water purification systems have been destroyed in cities where active hostilities are taking place. Also, people are not only forced to take water from the natural sources they find, but, unfortunately, sewage discharges are not cleaned. In particular, discharges from sewage facilities in Vasylyvka have been flowing into the Dnipro for 9 months. This will also have a negative impact, in particular on the potential bacteriological pollution of the river. This, first of all, will concern the lower part of the Dnipro.

On March 14, there was a shelling of the water treatment facilities of the Vasylyvsk Water Supply and Drainage Works (the village of Verkhnya Krynytsia, Zaporizhzhia Region). As a result, the building of the sewage pumping station No. 1, which supplies wastewater from the city of Vasylyvka to the sewage treatment plant, was destroyed. Return water from the city now enters the Dnipro without any treatment. Untreated discharges contain a large amount of organic substances, helminth eggs, pathogenic bacteria, sulfates, chlorides. Such pollution could lead to large-scale water blooms in the Dnieper and Black Sea with the onset of warmer weather.

Marine ecosystems

A wide range of military activities on land and at sea threaten Ukraine's marine ecosystems, while vulnerable and ecologically sensitive coastal habitats are directly affected by hostilities. Further research will be needed to determine the true impact of war on the ecology of the Black and Azov Seas, estuaries and wetlands, however, as these waters have already experienced a number of stresses from human activities such as pollution, overfishing, alien species invasions and climate change. , the consequences of exposure can be significant.

Violation of natural habitats

War and occupation have resulted in or exacerbated damage and disruption to a range of coastal and marine habitats, many of which are vulnerable or highly sensitive. However, in most cases it is difficult to determine the exact impact on populations of specific species without field studies. The following examples illustrate the range of threats that war poses to coastal and marine habitats.

The construction of trenches and fortifications destroys vegetation and increases soil erosion, and garbage and military waste pollute the soil and groundwater. With the movement of the front line, the line of physical destruction of natural habitats also shifts, especially where they are subjected to intense shelling. An example of this is the ecologically sensitive wetlands along the Dnieper estuary in the south of Kherson Oblast, which were used for fortification by Russia after its withdrawal from Kherson. In Crimea, according to reports, important coastal biotopes have been turned into military training grounds. In addition to physical destruction, noise pollution has an impact on bird and mammal species.

The fighting also affected marine habitats. Zmiiny Island became the site of intense hostilities from February to July with the use of heavy explosive and incendiary weapons. Part of the island and the surrounding waters were declared a conservation area in 1998, its terrestrial biodiversity has certainly suffered serious damage, the impact on the marine ecosystem is more difficult to assess.

Conclusions. During the detonation of rockets and artillery shells, a number of chemical compounds are formed: carbon monoxide (CO), carbon dioxide (CO₂), water vapor (H₂O), brown gas (NO), nitrous oxide (N₂O), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), formaldehyde (CH₂O), vapors of cyanic acid (HCN), nitrogen (N₂), as well as a large amount of toxic organic matter, the surrounding soils, wood, turf, structures are oxidized. From the first days, shelling and bombing of industrial and energy facilities, burning of forests, blowing up of oil depots, pollution of the Black and Azov Seas (primarily due to sinking of ships) were recorded. It will take a long time to restore the environment. If we talk about the restoration of forests to grow trees that are damaged, burned, then this is 30-20 years on average. Contamination of soils, for example by chemicals, as a result of explosions, conducting active hostilities, these are consequences for decades. The situation is similar to the restoration of marine ecosystems.

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**СИНТЕЗ S-БУТИЛКСАНТОГЕНАТОМЕТИЛДИАЛКИЛБОРАТОВ С ПОСЛЕДУЮЩИМ
ВЫЯВЛЕНИЕМ ЗАВИСИМОСТИ ИХ ПРОТИВОЗАДИРНОЙ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ОТ ДЛИНЫ
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**SYNTHESIS OF S-BUTYLXANTHOGENATOMETHYLDIALKYLBORATES WITH THE
SUBSEQUENT DETECTION OF THE DEPENDENCE OF THEIR EXTREME PRESSURE
EFFICIENCY ON THE LENGTH OF RADICALS INCLUDED IN THE BORONATE FRAGMENT**

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Синтезированы новые S-бутилксантогенатометилдиалкилбораты, строение которых доказано определением их элементного состава, физико-химических свойств и ИК-спектроскопией. Изучение противозадирных свойств, синтезированных соединений, на четырехшариковой машине трения (ЧМТ-1) показало высокую противозадирную эффективность S-бутилксантогенатометилдиметил- и дибутилборатов. Выявлена зависимость противозадирных свойств боратов от длины радикалов, входящих в состав боратного фрагмента.

ABSTRACT

New S-butylxanthogenatomethylalkylborates were synthesized, the structure of which was proved by determining their elemental composition, physicochemical properties, and IR spectroscopy. The study of the extreme